

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF USING THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM IN PREPARING STUDENTS FOR PURPOSE MANAGEMENT OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: In this article, the credit-module system is a process of educational organization, the evaluation model is calculated based on the collection of module technologies of teaching and the credit measure, the main tasks of the credit-module system and the credit-module system in preparing students for targeted management of preschool educational organizations it talks about the didactic possibilities of using the module system.

Key words: credit-module system, rating, independent education, new approach to education, final exam.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 in the preparation of intellectual potential personnel who have mastered the achievements of advanced science and technology with modern knowledge and skills in our country The system of continuous education organized on the basis of the concept of development is being improved.

In the sustainable development of the republic, "increasing the quality of training qualified personnel, adapting human capital to the requirements of the labor market, training highly qualified creative and systematic thinking personnel, who can make independent decisions based on international standards, is a necessary condition for the manifestation of their intellectual abilities and formation as a spiritual person. -creating conditions, forming a healthy competitive environment in the field, increasing its attractiveness, ensuring global competitiveness" are the strategic goals of higher education.

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an evaluation model based on the combination of module technologies of education and credit measurement.

According to the principle of the credit-module system, attention is paid to two important issues:

1. Ensuring the student's independent work.
2. Evaluation of students' knowledge based on rating.

The following are recognized as the main tasks of the credit module system:

- organization of the educational process based on modules;
- determining the value of one subject, course (credit);
- assessment of students' knowledge based on rating;
- to create an opportunity for students to create their study plans individually;
- increasing the share of independent education in the educational process;
- the convenience of educational programs and the ability to change based on the demand for a specialist in the labor market.

The introduction of the credit-module system in the higher education system is based not only on conducting the theoretical education process based on innovative educational technologies, but also on the independent study and learning of the student, a new attitude to education, and the demand of the labor market. It creates wide opportunities for training to acquire knowledge as well as to form practical skills, that is, this system is focused on professional training and personal development of students and allows future professionals to learn throughout their life. aimed at building and forming human capital that meets the labor market and modern requirements.

Credit (credit) is a unit of measurement of the educational load (time) spent on studying and mastering subjects in a particular educational field or program (course), i.e. credit is the minimum amount of time a student is allotted for classroom and independent study, usually one week, as determined by a normative document. Credit is given to the student after completing the assigned tasks in a certain subject and successfully passing the final exam.

At the undergraduate level, students must accumulate credits to obtain a diploma in their chosen field. Accumulated credit helps the student improve his skills throughout his life. In economic terms, accumulated credit becomes an academic "asset" of the student.

Another peculiarity of the credit-module system is that it gives students the right to choose subjects included in the working curriculum, thereby directly participating in the formation of an individual study plan. Also, students are given the freedom to choose not only subjects, but also professors. While giving students the opportunity to choose subjects is a positive thing, they also need to be able to assess which subjects they need to study in their field.

The credit system was first introduced in US universities in the 18th-19th centuries, and its purpose was to liberalize the educational process and determine the student's weekly study load. Thus, in 1869, the president of

Harvard University, Charles William Eliot, a famous figure of American education, introduced the concept of "credit hour" to science, and in 1870-1880, a system measured by credit hours was introduced. As a result, getting an education with the credit system and mastering educational programs created a great opportunity for students to independently plan the educational process, control its quality, and improve educational technologies.

The introduction of the measure of credit accumulation into the higher education system not only gave the student great freedom, but also allowed him to independently plan the academic process in order to become a competitive specialist in his chosen field in the future. At the same time, there was a need and need to improve the evaluation system and educational technologies.

The issue of approximation, unification and unification of the educational systems of different European countries appeared in the 70s of the last century.

By the end of the 20th century, the participation of higher education institutions in international educational programs in Europe became an important issue, and the internationalization of higher education educational programs became one of the urgent directions of development. ERASMUS (European Community Action Scheme for Mobility of University Students) educational program of student exchange, founded by the European Union in 1987, was considered the most exemplary and was introduced in 12 European countries. Based on the accumulated experiences, it was accepted as a pump for the new SOCRATES program, which was specialized in the education of all age groups, and this program was planned until 2006 and was implemented in 31 countries. In addition, Leonardo Da Vinci and Tempus-Taxis educational programs aimed at strengthening the image of Europe as a cradle of science and universities were implemented in Europe under the student exchange program.

However, in the implementation of these programs in Europe, diversity and inconsistencies have arisen, and generalization difficulties have arisen. In order to overcome these problems, there was a need to bring national education systems closer together, make them flexible and transparent, and create a system that serves to make education documents easily comparable. The ESTS (European Credit Transfer System) system, which was created as a pilot project of the ERASMUS program and was experimentally tested for 6 years in 1989-1995, was recognized as such a system, and 145 higher educational institutions of Europe participated in it.

From the 90s, the process of modernization of the education system based on the Bologna system began to be observed in developed countries. The main

goal of the Bologna system is to create a single field for higher education on a global scale.

On June 19, 1999, at a special conference held in Bologna, Italy, the education ministers of 29 European countries adopted the Bologna Declaration, and this date was set as the official date of the process. In this, the main attention was paid to the ESTS and pan-European diploma application, and the task of the credit-module system was not to create a unified higher education system in 2010, but to achieve international "transparency" and promote the existing education systems and qualifications of states and HEIs. Adaptation was established while preserving the autonomy in the field of regional policy.

To date, almost all European countries have reformed their national higher education systems, introduced the credit-module system, however, they differ sharply from each other due to their focus on the solution of national socio-economic problems, that is, each it can be seen that a country has tried to preserve its unique educational system, national, historical and cultural traditions.

As a result, the ESTS system, which cannot be logically rejected in Europe, was created, which is necessary for maximum approximation and equalization of the evaluation scales of national systems according to the pan-European model. According to it, on average, a student must collect 60 European credits in one academic year.

Issues related to the organization of the educational process in the credit-module system in higher education in Uzbekistan are covered in detail in the study guide created by B.Sh.Usmanov and R.A.Khabibullayev. According to the authors, the introduction of the Bologna Declaration envisages the introduction of a two-stage higher education, where the first stage is aimed at acquiring executive skills suitable for the production needs of students, and the second - at developing creative abilities.

The main tasks of higher education in the credit-module system are as follows:

- trained specialists of a new form with extensive fundamental knowledge, who are enterprising, adaptable to the changing requirements of the labor and technology market;
- increasing interest in providing quality education services by democratizing the higher education system;

- development and implementation of mechanisms that determine the responsibility of leaders to strengthen the rights of students to receive quality education, provide quality educational services.

These tasks are carried out by improving the technology of organizing the educational process taking into account the interests of students and creating healthy competition between professors and teachers.

Therefore, in our research, we considered it necessary to study the possibilities of the credit-module system and scientific-theoretical analysis of this issue in directing students who have interests, inclinations and desires to target management of preschool educational organizations to management activities.

For this purpose, in the program of preschool education, comprehensive professional training, including the acquisition of the basis of knowledge in specialized subjects by taking into account the general, integrated aspects of professional activity, developing professional creativity and forming independent knowledge skills, including pre-school education of students it is also necessary to consider the preparation of lim organizations for targeted management.

The process of teaching preschool students of higher education institutions is a complex process that includes such directions as the development of organizational, management, and cognitive activities in the preparation of a highly educated specialist, which is mainly an educational process. consists of training and control processes.

Educational activities include all types of academic activities, independent study of students and professional practices. The monitoring process allows you to determine the extent to which students have mastered the educational program.

Compulsory subjects of the curriculum of preschool education are listed in the qualification requirements, which include subjects that must be mastered. In the content of compulsory subjects, there are opportunities for the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications for preparing students for management activities, and by creating conditions for the development of necessary competencies based on a systematic approach to the teaching of these subjects, it is possible to prepare for the purposeful management of a preschool educational organization

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